

The Alkaloids of Kurchee Bark (*Holarrhena Antidysenterica*). Part I.

A Preliminary Note on Two New Alkaloids discovered in Indian *Holarrhena*.

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A large volume of chemical work has been done on the alkaloids of *Holarrhena* both in Europe and in India. The present work was undertaken with a view to study the pharmacological action of the alkaloids present in Indian *Holarrhena*. The recent work of Chopra and Ghosh (*Indian Medical Gazette*, 1927, **62**, 132,) on the pharmacological action of conessin has aroused wide interest in the alkaloids of *Kurchee* as a good drug. It was thought desirable to make a systematic study of the action of the individual alkaloids in *Kurchee* and also to see if the total alkaloids could be utilised and the product made into an article of commerce.

As a result of this investigation, two new alkaloids have been isolated in addition to conessin already known to be present in the bark of *Holarrhena antidysenterica*. The present paper records only the detailed method of their isolation and also some decisive evidences as to their being quite new alkaloids. Further work on these alkaloids is in progress and the full analytical data will be communicated later.

Ulrici (*Archiv. Pharm.*, 1918, **256**, 57) worked on the bark of *Holarrhena africana* and described in detail the isolation of the different alkaloids in it. He found the following alkaloids: (1) Conessin, $C_{23}H_{33}N_3$, large cubical crystals (unstable), m.p. 125° ; also needles m.p. 121.5° ; (2) a base $C_{24}H_{40}N_3$, of m.p. 121.5° and (3) homoconessin (dimethylconessin $C_{26}H_{42}N_3$) broad needles, m.p. not given. Giemsa and Halberkann (*Archiv. Pharm.*, 1918, **256**, 201), however, working on the same bark isolated only conessin $C_{24}H_{40}N_3$, which crystallises in flat needles or tablets, melting at 123° - 124° . The homoconessin of Ulrici was found by them to be identical with conessin.

Pyman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **115**, 163), who worked on the alkaloids of *Holarrhena congolensis*, Stapf., found the following: (1) Conessine, $C_{24}H_{40}N_2$, large colourless plates, m.p. 125° and (2) holarrhenine, $C_{24}H_{38}ON_2$, silky needles, m.p. $197^\circ-198^\circ$; $[\alpha]_D = -7.1^\circ$ (in $CHCl_3$); $[\alpha]_D$ of $C_{24}H_{38}ON_2 \cdot 2HBr = +12.1^\circ$.

Kanga, Ayyar and Simonsen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **129**, 2123) working on the seeds of Indian *Kurchee* (*Holarrhena antidysenterica*) isolated only pure conessine, $C_{24}H_{40}N_2$, m.p. $120^\circ-121^\circ$ (125° when crystallised from acetone) and studied some of its decomposition products.

Recently, Caius and Mhaskar (*Indian Medical Research Memoir*, No. 6, May, 1927) made a detailed study of both the seeds and bark of Indian *Kurchee*. They found only 0.025% of alkaloid in the seeds and 0.022% in the bark. They have isolated and purified only conessine and described in detail some of the colour reactions and tests of this alkaloid already studied carefully by Pyman. No mention is however, found in the published literature about the isolation of any other alkaloid in Indian *Holarrhena*.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A preliminary *assay* for the total alkaloids was made as follows: 20 gm. of the finely powdered bark (60 mesh) were treated with 10 c.c. ammonia (1:5) and then with 400 c.c. of a mixture of ether and chloroform. The mixture was agitated for 3 hours, 20 c.c. of water were added to it, agitated again and then allowed to settle. 200 C.c. of the clear, supernatant liquid (representing 10 g. of the bark) were filtered off into a separating funnel and shaken up repeatedly with dilute sulphuric acid till the whole of the alkaloid passed into the acid. The acid extract was filtered, made alkaline with ammonia and again taken up with chloroform. The chloroform solution was washed, transferred to a weighed vessel, the solvent carefully removed and the substance dried to a constant weight. The yield of total alkaloid was 1.28% of the weight of the dry bark. Exhaustion of the powdered bark with 95% alcohol in a Soxhlet, extraction of the residue with dilute acid and taking up the alkaloid with chloroform after adding excess of alkali gave nearly the same quantity of total alkaloids.

Preparation of total Alkaloids.—For complete examination, about two maunds (164 lbs.) of the powdered bark were percolated in the cold with rectified spirit till nearly exhausted. The major portion of the alcohol was distilled off and the remainder was then removed in partial vacuum. Two maunds of the bark thus gave 11 lbs. 6 oz. of the dark green, soft extract. It was repeatedly extracted with dilute hydrochloric acid until the last portion of the acid solution was nearly free from alkaloids. The acid solution was then carefully neutralised with dilute caustic soda and filtered. The filtrate was shaken with ether which removed some resinous, non-alkaloidal impurities. The aqueous liquid was then treated with slight excess of NaOH under constant stirring and the liquid kept cool by ice. The granular precipitate of the alkaloid was filtered and washed until free from excess of alkali. It was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid, made alkaline with caustic soda and shaken repeatedly with CHCl_3 . The chloroform extract was washed, dried with anhydrous potassium carbonate, filtered and distilled. The residue was dried in vacuum over sulphuric acid. The quantity of alkaloid thus obtained was about 10% of the weight of the extract and about 0.7% of the weight of the bark. The large scale extraction with alcohol was done in a factory and the yield was, therefore, much less than what we obtained in our laboratory.

Separation and Purification of the Alkaloids.—The separation of the alkaloids is based on the principle that the tartrates of kurchicine and conessine are very slightly soluble in 95% alcohol, whereas the tartrate of the low-melting alkaloid kurchine, is freely soluble in it. Again the sulphate of kurchicine is practically insoluble in cold water whereas the sulphate of conessine is more soluble in it. Kurchicine is practically insoluble in petroleum ether whereas conessine is fairly soluble. The low-melting alkaloid is freely soluble in petroleum ether.

The total alkaloid was dissolved in 95% alcohol (4 to 6 times the weight of alkaloid taken) and to it was carefully added a saturated solution of tartaric acid in absolute alcohol until neutralised. The white, amorphous precipitate (A) obtained was filtered off and washed several times with 95% alcohol. It was then dissolved in the smallest amount of boiling water, the solution treated with animal charcoal, filtered, and reprecipitated by adding excess of absolute alcohol. The tartrate was thus obtained as a white, amorphous powder. It was dissolved in water, the alkaloid liberated by NaOH

and taken up with CHCl_3 . The CHCl_3 solution was washed, dried with K_2CO_3 and concentrated to a small bulk. A slight excess of petroleum ether was added when crystals began to appear. After several hours, the crystals (tufts of needles) were separated from the mother-liquor and washed with petroleum ether. They were redissolved in the smallest amount of CHCl_3 and crystallised again by addition of petroleum ether. The substance began to melt at 173° and it was complete at 175° . The amount of this new alkaloid (designated "kurchicine") was about 0.12% of the weight of the bark.

The substance was further purified by dissolving in hot dilute sulphuric acid, concentrating to a small bulk and allowing it to cool. The sulphate crystallised out in bright, colourless plates. It was almost insoluble in cold water. It was recrystallised from hot water and the base then liberated by dilute alkali and washed until free from alkali. The dried base was washed with small quantities of ether, redissolved in a small amount of chloroform and crystallised by addition of petroleum ether. The substance forms colourless needles, m.p. 175° . It is easily soluble in alcohol, fairly soluble in chloroform, slightly soluble in ether and nearly insoluble in petroleum ether.

The mother-liquors from kurchicine were evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in the smallest amount of chloroform and precipitated by petroleum ether. Only a small crop of crystals was obtained. The filtrate gave conessine, which on recrystallisation melted at 120° .

The alcoholic mother-liquor from the precipitate (A) was evaporated to dryness in vacuum. The residue was treated with 95% alcohol and a portion was found insoluble. The solution was filtered and evaporated to dryness in *vacuo*. The residue was dissolved in water, the alkaloid liberated by caustic soda and taken up with petroleum ether. The petroleum ether was removed and the base obtained as a soft, yellowish mass, which gradually hardened on keeping. The crystallisation of the substance was a very long and tedious affair. The hydrochloride could only be obtained as an amorphous mass by passing dry hydrochloric acid gas in dry ethereal solution but it was very soluble in water and hygroscopic. The nitrate, phosphate, hydrobromide, tartrate, oxalate, all failed to crystallise. The crude base could not be made to crystallise from any solvent. After several trials, the sulphate was crystallised in

the following way: The base was dissolved in dilute sulphuric acid, the solution being kept neutral. It was concentrated below 60° under reduced pressure. On keeping the concentrated solution for 3 or 4 days, microscopic needles of the sulphate gradually separated. These were transferred to a Buchner funnel, washed with absolute alcohol and recrystallised from water. The pure sulphate was then dissolved in water, the alkaloid liberated by caustic soda and taken up with ether. The ethereal solution was dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and on concentration gave tufts of white needles. The base melts at 75° and the m.p. is not altered by recrystallisation. Owing to the difficulty of crystallising this low-melting alkaloid, it could not be obtained in quantitative yield. This alkaloid forms, however, the largest proportion of the total alkaloids present in *Kurchee* bark and a study of its pharmacological action will determine the suitability of the bark as an economic product.

A study of the properties and some of the analytical results shows that kurchicine is quite different from holarrhenine. Holarrhenine melts at 197°-198°, while the m.p. of kurchicine after repeated crystallisation did not rise above 175°. The nitrogen content of holarrhenine is 7.56%, while that of kurchicine is 8.53% (average of 4 combustions). The specific rotation of holarrhenine in CHCl₃ is -7.1°, while that of kurchicine is nearly -10°. The specific rotation of holarrhenine hydrobromide, B. 2HBr. 3H₂O, in water is +11.0°, while that of kurchicine hydrobromide (anhydrous) is -18.75°.

The low-melting alkaloid, for which the name "kurchine" is suggested, is also a new alkaloid (m.p. 75°). It is easily soluble in alcohol, chloroform, ether and petroleum ether. The nitrogen content was found to be 9.84% (average of 3 combustions), while that of conessine is 7.86%.

Summary.

(1) The content of alkaloids in Indian *Kurchee* bark is found to be about 1.2 per cent.

(2) A new method is described in detail for the separation of the individual alkaloids.

(3) Two new alkaloids, besides conessine, have been discovered and are designated kurchicine and kurchine respectively, the latter being present in the largest amount.

(4) Some decisive evidences for the two new alkaloids are adduced as a preliminary report.

(5) From the amount of the total alkaloids present, it will be quite economical to prepare salts of the alkaloids in a commercial scale, if the alkaloids give satisfactory clinical results.

(6) The method of separation devised will enable one to eliminate the more toxic alkaloid, if there be any.

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